

THE EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE AND VISCOSITY ON THE FLUORESCENCE OF SOLUTIONS OF SOME ORGANIC COMPOUNDS, USING UV EXCITATION

BY J. SAHU

The effect of temperature and viscosity on the fluorescence of solutions of some organic compounds, using UV excitation in low viscosity (petroleum ether and ethanol) and high viscosity (medicinal paraffin and glycerol), in the temperature range varying from -70° to 70° has been investigated. Terphenyl and carbazole have unit yields in all the solvents over the temperature range studied. Acenaphthene, 2,6-dimethylnaphthalene, naphthalene, stilbene and phenanthrene show flattish yield-temperature curves. The yields of ethyl stilbene-4:4'-dicarboxylate and stilbene-4:4'-bis-carbonimino-ethyl ether are markedly temperature-dependent, reach unity at low temperatures and have a large viscosity effect. The F_0 values of 1- and 2-naphthols in non-ionised and ionised forms are also temperature-dependent. The F_0 value in general increases with the increase of viscosity. The results are interpreted by an equation:

$$(1/F - 1) = k e^{-E/RT} + K.$$

In previous publications (Bowen and Sahu, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1959, **63**, 4; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 3716) the effect of temperature and viscosity on the fluorescence of solutions of anthracene and its derivatives, and acridine and acridone, using excitation 3650 Å line of mercury, was studied. The present work deals with the results of a similar study on solutions of some other organic compounds.

EXPERIMENTAL

The experimental method adopted was that of Bowen and Sahu (*loc. cit.*) with the following changes:

(a) The 3135 Å line of mercury (with nearly 10% of 3340 Å line) was secured as exciting light by removing the glass envelope of the mercury lamp and filtering the radiation through a strong solution of nickel and cobalt sulphates containing some copper sulphate.

(b) The glass prism of the spectrometer and the glass tube for holding the fluorescent solutions, fitted in the glass Quickfit flask, were all replaced by the silica ones.

(c) Solutions used were dilute enough to afford only partial light absorption.

(d) The spectrometer was adjusted to right angles to the exciting light to pick up the maximum fluorescence emission. This was tested for the satisfactory work by measuring the fluorescence of anthracene solutions in petroleum ether (b.p. 80-100°) (using a concentration providing maximum collectable fluorescence) at different temperatures.

As it was not possible to calibrate the apparatus directly after making the above changes, a terphenyl solution in petroleum ether ($c = 10^{-4}$ M/l), its F_0 value being known to be unity, was chosen to act as the standard on account of its fluorescence band lying in the region in which those of the other compounds of study also fell. The F_0 values of the compounds were found by comparing the area under the experimentally found fluorescence band of the standard with those of the others on the assumption that the percentage correction for the sensitivity of the apparatus and that for the overlap effect would be the same for all the compounds having fluorescence bands in the same regions. However, the F_0 value of phenanthrene on comparison with that of anthracene ($F_0 = 0.332$), obtained by using solutions of known absolute yield (Weber and Teale, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1957, **53**, 646) and terphenyl ($F_0 = 1.0$), all in petroleum ether (80-100°), was found approximately to be the same (0.155 with anthracene standard and 0.159 with terphenyl standard). The results after correction for refractive index are recorded in Table I and the effect of temperature and viscosity on the fluorescence of organic compounds in solutions is shown in Fig. 1.

TABLE I

Fluorescence of organic substances in solutions.							
Compounds.	Solvents.	Region of fluorescence band.	F_0 at 20°.	Compounds.	Solvents.	Region of fluorescence band.	F_0 at 20°.
1. Phenanthrene	P		0.155	7. Stilbene-4:4'-bis-carboniminoethyl ether	E	4500-3500	0.425 0.610
	E	4200-3400 Å	0.210		G		
	M		0.188	8. Carbazole	P	4200-2900	0.950 1.000
2. Naphthalene	P	3700-3000	0.393	9. <i>p</i> -Terphenyl	P	4100-2950	1.000
3. 2:6-Dimethylnaphthalene	P	3800-2900	0.390	10. 1-Naphthol	(a) Neutral EtOH (mol. form)	4700-3300 (max. at 3600 Å)	0.635
4. Acenaphthene	P	3900-3200	0.660		(b) Alkaline EtOH (ionic form)	5700-3800 (max. at 4700 Å)	0.590
5. Stilbene	P	3800-2800	0.267	11. 2-Naphthol	(a) Neutral EtOH (mol. form)	4500-2900 (max. at 3550 Å)	0.590
	M		0.267		(b) Alkaline EtOH (ionic form)	5900-3700 (max. at 4225 Å)	0.465
6. Ethyl stilbene-4:4'-dicarboxylate	E G	4500-3500	0.360 0.500				

N.B.—P, M, G and E refer respectively to petroleum ether (80-100°), medicinal paraffin, glycerol and ethanol.

DISCUSSION

The results are interpreted making assumption of the following simple mechanism :

Processes.	Relative rates.
$A + h\nu \rightarrow {}^1A^*$.. (1)	1
${}^1A^* \longrightarrow A + h\nu'$.. (2)	$k_1 [{}^1A^*]$
${}^1A^* \longrightarrow {}^3A$.. (3)	$k_2 [e^{-E/RT}] [{}^1A^*]$
${}^1A^* \longrightarrow A \text{ or } {}^3A$.. (4)	$k_3 [{}^1A^*]$

Processes (1) and (2) only are in operation for carbazole and terphenyl which has a quantum yield, so that $(1/F-1) = 0$. For acenaphthene, 2:6-dimethylnaphthalene, naphthalene, stilbene and phenanthrene, which show flattish yield-temperature curves, all the above four processes are in operation; for ethyl stilbene-4:4'-dicarboxylate and stilbene-4:4'-bis-carboniminoethyl ether and 1- and 2-naphthols, in non-ionic and ionic forms, the first three processes are in operation. The process (3) is suggested on the basis of the simple hypothesis that out of the two processes of energy degradation, one temperature-dependent with a large viscosity effect and the other temperature-independent, the former may be due to the return of singlet excited molecules to the triplet undergoing some bent or twisted configuration (assuming some energy of activation) whose amplitude of bending or twisting is restricted in highly viscous solvents. Equation (4) is proposed to explain the temperature-independent process. In this process whether the singlet excited molecules return to the normal state through a non-radiational process or to the triplet state needing no energy of activation, is very difficult to suggest. If the return to the normal state through a non-radiational process is the only possible one, then the compounds would not be expected to phosphoresce efficiently at low temperatures. It has been suggested by Livingston ("Photochemistry of Liquid and Solid States", John Wiley & Sons, Inc., 1960, p. 77, that in the photo-oxidation of anthracene in bromobenzene, the singlet excited molecules may partly return directly to the normal

state through a non-radiational process. If it is so, then the compounds showing flattish yield-temperature curves might have their triplet state curves crossing the singlet excited curves above the zero-vibrational level of the latter, and their singlet curves closely approximating to the ground level potential energy curves near the minimum so that the singlet excited molecules may pass over to the triplet level with some small energy of activation and also to the normal state directly

FIG. 1

The numbers and symbols in Fig. 1 correspond respectively to the compounds and solvents shown in Table I.

with little activation energy, whereby the fluorescence yields do not reach unity at low temperatures; the reverse may also be true.

The compounds having unit yields over the whole temperature range then return from the singlet excited state through a radiational process only to the normal state, as might occur if the triplet state curves crossed the singlet excited state curves much above the zero-vibrational level of the latter and the singlet excited state curves did not closely touch the normal potential energy curves.

The compounds showing steep temperature-dependent yields and those reaching unity at low temperatures might have then the triplet state curves crossing the singlet excited above the zero-vibrational level of the latter, but the singlet excited not touching the normal.

Change of viscosity definitely produces a considerable effect on the fluorescence yields, but it has not been possible to interpret the effect clearly; however, the tentative explanation advanced by Bowen and Sahu (*loc. cit.*), may also be applicable in these cases.

From the equation :

$$(1/F - 1) = k e^{-E/RT} + K$$

(which can be deduced from the above mechanism) the values of E and k for some compounds have been calculated (Table II).

TABLE II

* Compounds.	** Solvents.	E .	k .
(6)	E	4300 cal./mol.	2760
	G	4700	3067
(7)	E	5500	16000
	G	6000	16800
(10)	E	3000	95
	E	2850	92
(11)	E	1850	16.4
	E	850	5.0

* The number of compounds corresponds to those shown in Table I.

** Symbols have the same significance as in Table I.

The E -values of the ionised and non-ionised forms of both the 1- and 2-naphthols differ from each other. This difference is much more marked in 2-naphthol than in 1-naphthol. This may be ascribed to ionisation effecting a considerable change in the electronic structure of the molecules (Bowen and Wokes, "Fluorescence of Solutions", 1953, p. 10).

Oxygen Quenching.—Quenching of fluorescence of solutions of these organic compounds by oxygen has also been studied. Phenanthrene in petroleum ether has a marked oxygen-quenching effect whereas in ethanol its fluorescence is not quenched. Naphthalene, 2:6-dimethylnaphthalene, acenaphthene and carbazole, all in petroleum ether, show oxygen quenching, whereas stilbene and its derivatives do not show any quenching by oxygen.

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